

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The commonest is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Could be dark or light brown (cinnamon), sometimes even white. Not at all times black in shade. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear could be found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Size: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six feet in length. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, however their fur can range from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are some of one of the best at climbing timber. Their relatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb timber for protection, food, and even hibernation. The majority of their food regimen is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Food regimen: Their various weight-reduction plan gives them the power to live in a big vary of habitats. In addition they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They're the probably bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are essentially the most widespread of all bear species, discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center [chimpanzee](#) [teddy bear](#) East. Grizzlies are responsible for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per year. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and reduced habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a large variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big construct, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the ideas, which led to the name of the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt young mammals resembling elk and moose. Their colour varies from gentle blonde to dark brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 toes lengthy, and have a shoulder top of 3. Three ft. □□ Food regimen: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been recognized to prey on massive mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than those discovered within the Rocky Mountains on account of a richer weight-reduction plan. Every year there are forty six attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Identified for his or her aggressive behavior, grizzlies are chargeable for the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are nearly as giant as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1, four hundred pounds, eight feet lengthy, and four ft tall on the shoulder. □□ Diet: Their diet is just like mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, as a result of more plentiful meals sources, the islands can assist a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to turn out to be their very own subspecies. This has led to a more advanced social construction which leads to much less conflict between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. On account of their isolation, there is just one attack on people each different 12 months. Largest species of bear on the earth weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food regimen is usually made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white however is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 feet tall. They're a threatened species on account of lack of habitat from local weather change. Despite their enormous dimension polar bears may be quick, sustaining a 6 mph tempo in the water. □□ Options: In comparison with different bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their eating regimen consists largely of animals, particularly seals which they'll smell from a mile away. Although they appear white, their fur is actually clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears might be extraordinarily harmful. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are rare because of the remote nature of their habitat. Identified for its cream coloration chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and sometimes common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered susceptible. □□ Measurement: One of the smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Diet: Depending on the season it generally feeds on small mammals,

birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on people are growing as people encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They are one among the simplest bears to tame (and due to this fact common in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered solely in China. 99% of its weight loss plan is bamboo. In reality, the second individual in historical past to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas defending his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered solely in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 remain within the wild and they are thought of a weak species. □□ Dimension: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and may be over 4 ft tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at delivery. It also has a close cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical pattern in light brown and white. □□ Food regimen: Unlike other bears the panda's weight-reduction plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Options: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo retains them regular: they poop over 40 instances a day! □□ Harmful? Assaults are rare but dangerous, on condition that pandas have one in all the highest chew forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is discovered in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is unsure however thought of susceptible and on the decline because of loss of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and other body components utilized in conventional medicines. □□ Dimension: They stand only 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a short snout. They are named for his or her pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that appears like a rising solar. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Food regimen: Solar bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." The truth is, they have an extremely lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? Attributable to its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the title sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of lower than 20,000, they're thought-about susceptible. □□ Dimension: They are fifty five to seventy five inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Features: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're simple to tell aside from other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very quick and might out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their big curved claws. □□ Food regimen: Their diet consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Dangerous? They're one of the most aggressive bears, with the most attacks on people, largely due to shock encounters. They blow the mud around with large puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 feet away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not combine well with rhinos and elephants, usually charging at one another when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's final quick-confronted bear. The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that look like glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Measurement: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last short-faced bear and the only bear native to South America. □□ Features: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that sometimes seem like glasses. They spend most of their time in trees where they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. □□ Food plan: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a weight loss plan consisting of mostly cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they are going to opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Harmful? Residing in distant mountains, these shy bears would be the least dangerous of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is nearer to the polar bear. They function the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, just like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, however haven't been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA assessments have been unable to determine what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas are not bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in area. Most bear assaults occur when a bear is startled or defending their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their very own family that are closer

cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks which will point out a bear is nearby, through which case you need to be additional vigilant. Listed below are a number of ideas you need to use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies protected. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't by accident startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** Whereas you could have great intentions, a bear is prone to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** If you see a bear, don't try to strategy or feed it. This contains food, but also your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you choose, make sure it's no less than 200 feet away out of your tent so you don't attract bears to your campsite. 4. **Keep CALM.** Should you meet a bear, do not run. Try to make yourself look as massive as potential, waving your arms above your head. You can also lengthen a jacket above your head to make yourself look larger. Lock these items in a bear canister or use a bear bag to grasp them up in a tree. Do not scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Speak to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Combat Back.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, do not play dead. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8. Zero to 8.4 toes long, and 4.0 to 5.25 feet tall, the largest bear by each size and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Struggle back with all of your strength and hope that it's going to again down. Which bear is the most dangerous? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is thought for essentially the most assaults. When in bear nation, it's at all times smart to carry bear spray. It's effectively deserved, especially when cubs are round. Every year there are roughly forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to loss of life. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most likely to see an American black bear, on average there is only one attack per yr. By way of raw bite power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's bite reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When using the bite drive quotient (chew power relative to measurement), the sun bear packs probably the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fire but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he became an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-running public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear recognized for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired countless through-hikers to attempt to master the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a duty-free life-style. He also could be the first bear to receive his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son usually would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near where he was from. Chris also wrote How to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal components backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to supply fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and the way-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

